

A new emerging ecofriendly rare earth free 2D luminescent nanoprobe for high-contrast *in vitro* and *in vivo* imaging applications

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Abstract

A new emerging ecofriendly rare-earth free, highly luminescent and biocompatible two dimensional (2D) carbon based boron oxynitride (BCNO) was synthesized using facile auto-combustion method which can be easily scaled-up for large quantities. [1] The BCNO exhibits a single, distinct and broad photoluminescence (PL) emission which can be easily tuned from violet to deep red (342 nm to 654 nm) by varying the amount of boron/carbon content. Moreover, time resolved photoluminescence (TRPL) reveals that 2D BCNO have PL lifetime in range of nanosecond. PL and TRPL results indicate that B-O act as luminescence centers, which are responsible for the tunable luminescent properties while carbon impurity induce energy levels in the band gap of 2D BCNO nanophosphors. These tunable and biocompatible luminescent 2D BCNO nanophosphors are potentially used for *in vitro* high-contrast cellular imaging as well as *in vivo* imaging applications.

Keywords: BCNO, photoluminescence, time resolved photoluminescence, *in vitro*, *in vivo*.

References

1. B. K. Gupta et al, RSC Advances 7 (2017) 41486-41494.